

Halogenation. Part III. Bromination.

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Bromination of aromatic hydrocarbons has been effected directly in presence as well as in absence of halogen carriers. Bromobenzene has been obtained from boiling benzene and bromine vapour by Couper (*Annalen*, 1857, 104, 225). Brunner has effected the bromination of benzene by one molecule of bromine at the room temperature in 150 days up to 94 per cent. (*Chem. Zentr.*, 1900, II, 251). Bromination has also been brought about in the presence of 1—2 per cent. of iodine (Schramm *Ber.*, 1885, 18, 515; Michaelis and Groff, *Ber.*, 1875, 8, 926), in the presence of aluminium-mercury couple (Cohen and Dakin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1899, 76, 894), in the presence of zinc chloride (Schiaparelli, *Gazzetta*, 1881, 11, 70), in the presence of aluminium chloride (Green, *Compt. rend.*, 1880, 90, 41) and in the presence of pyridine (Cross and Cohen, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1908).

Gattermann ("Die Praxis des Organischen Chemikers") obtained bromobenzene in the presence of iron filings. A few cases of bromination with aqueous hypobromous acid (Stark, *Ber.*, 1913, 46, 670) have also been effected. Datta and Chatterjee (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 38, 2545) introduced bromine in the aromatic hydrocarbons by means of bromine and concentrated nitric acid, but the yield of the bromo-compound, by this method, has not been found to be satisfactory by the authors.

Attempts have been made by the authors in this investigation to bring about bromination in presence of (i) a mixture of nitro-sulphonic acid and fuming nitric acid, (ii) concentrated or fuming sulphuric acid, (iii) concentrated or fuming nitric acid, (iv) a mixture of concentrated or fuming sulphuric acid and concentrated or fuming nitric acid, and (v) sodium nitrite and concentrated or fuming sulphuric acid.

The results obtained by using a mixture of nitro-sulphonic acid and fuming nitric acid are summarised in Table I. It has been found possible by this method to get 10.8 g. of bromobenzene from 10 c.c. of benzene and 3 c.c. of bromine, a yield which has not been obtained by any method known up till now when the amount of bromine used in the experiment is taken into consideration.

In the methods of Cross and Cohen (*loc. cit.*) and of Gattermann (*loc. cit.*) which are generally used in the laboratory for preparing bromobenzene, a much larger quantity (8 c.c.) of bromine is used to obtain about 12 g. of bromobenzene from 10 g of benzene.

It is interesting to find that while the presence of a small quantity of acetic acid in iodination is capable of increasing the yield of iodo-compounds to a considerable extent (Varma and Kulkarni, this *Journal*, 1926, 3, 291; Varma and Panickar, *ibid*, 1926, 3, 342), the presence of acetic acid has no appreciable effect in the case of bromination.

In addition to bromobenzene, it has been possible in the presence of this mixture of nitro-sulphonic acid and fuming nitric acid to get a good yield of *p*-dibromobenzene from benzene itself or from bromobenzene, *p*-bromo-iodobenzene from iodobenzene, *o*- and *p*-bromo-toluene and penta-brom-benzoic acid from toluene, bromo-xylenes from *p*-xylene. *o*-Chlorotoluene and *p*-iodotoluene are oxidised to chlorobenzoic and iodobenzoic acids respectively.

Bromination has also been effected in presence of sulphuric acid. The results obtained are summarised in Table II. Concentrated sulphuric acid gives but a poor yield of the bromo-derivative whilst fuming sulphuric acid containing 10 per cent. of sulphur trioxide gives as much as 8.8 g. of bromobenzene from 10 c.c. of benzene and 5 c.c. of bromine. This yield is lower than that obtained by using the nitro-sulphonic acid mixture. The formation of the sulphonic acid derivative as the intermediate product during the course of the reaction does not seem probable as benzene sulphonic acid itself is not affected at all by bromine (*vide* Table II, Expt. 18).

Nitric acid is also capable of bringing about bromination. The results are summarised in Table III. The yield of the bromo-derivative is very poor when concentrated nitric acid alone is used but fuming nitric acid (*d* 1.52) gives a better yield, nearly the same that is obtained by using fuming sulphuric acid. A mixture of fuming sulphuric acid and fuming nitric acid (equal volumes of each) is equally effective though not better than any one of them.

The presence of sodium nitrite and sulphuric acid also brings about bromination but the yield is far short of that obtained by using the nitro-sulphonic acid mixture. The results are summarised in Table IV. In this case the use of fuming sulphuric acid does not seem to have any clear advantage over that of ordinary concentrated sulphuric acid.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Bromination in presence of fuming nitric and nitro-sulphonic acid mixture.

The above mixture is prepared by passing a steady current of dry sulphur dioxide into cold fuming nitric acid (d 1.52) until about 50 per cent. of nitro-sulphonic acid is obtained. If the percentage of nitro-sulphonic acid in the mixture is greater than 50 per cent., it is brought down to this value by adding to it the required quantity of fuming nitric acid. A mixture thus prepared is used in the following experiments.

In the experiments tabulated below, benzene and bromine are taken in a round-bottomed flask and heated on a water-bath under reflux condenser. The nitro-sulphonic acid mixture is then added from the upper end of the condenser tube, one c.c. at a time, at intervals of ten minutes. When the whole of the mixture is added the contents of the flask are heated for a further period mentioned against the experiments, and in some cases, left to stand for some hours or overnight. The reacting mixture is then washed twice with distilled water in a separating funnel and subsequently with a very dilute caustic soda solution. It is finally again washed with distilled water and then dehydrated with fused calcium chloride and distilled. The fraction distilling between 150° and 170° is first collected. This fraction is re-distilled and the portion now distilling at 155° - 165° is collected separately and found to be mono-bromo-benzene. The residue, if any, left in the distilling flask is crystallised from rectified spirit and identified.

It is clear from the above table that any attempt to get a better yield of mono-bromobenzene by increasing the period of heating on the water-bath or by increasing the quantity of the nitro-sulphonic acid mixture or of bromine results in the decrease of the yield.

Bromination in presence of concentrated or fuming sulphuric acid.—The procedure adopted in this case is exactly the same as that mentioned in the preceding one. Here only concentrated sulphuric acid (d 1.84) or fuming sulphuric acid containing 10 per cent. of SO_3 is used in place of the nitro-sulphonic acid mixture used in the preceding case. The results obtained are summarised in Table II.

TABLE I.

Expt.	Benzene (in c.c.)	Bromine (in c.c.)	Acetic acid.	Nitro- sulpho- nic mix- ture (in c.c.)	Time al- lowed for reaction (in hrs)	Monobromo- derivative (in gm.)	Di- or poly- bromo or other derivatives.
1	10	3	...	6	3	8.6	Very little re- sidue left.
2	"	"	3 c.c.	"	"	8.9	" "
3	"	"	4 "	"	"	8.5	" "
4	"	"	"	10	"	10.2	" "
5	"	"	"	"	4	10.8	" "
6	"	"	"	13	"	9.1	Some residue left.
7	"	"	2 c.c.	10	3	8.8	0.9 g. of 1:3:5- tri-bromoben- zene.
8	"	6	"	10	"	9.0	2.1 g. of <i>p</i> -di- bromobenzene.
9	"	3	"	10	4*	very little	3.8 g. of <i>p</i> -di- bromobenzene.
10	"	6	"	"	4*	"	6.0 g. of <i>p</i> -di- bromobenzene.
11	Chloroben- zene 5 g.	1.4	"	"	4*	Bromo-chlo- robenzene (3.5 g.).	
12	Bromoben- zene (10 c.c.)	2.4	"	"	4*	<i>p</i> -Dibromo- benzene (6.2 g.).	
13	Iodobenzene (3.5 c.c.)	0.9	"	"	5 (days)	<i>p</i> -Bromo- iodo-benzene (2.6 g.).	
14	" 10 c.c.	2.9	"	10	4	<i>p</i> -Bromo- iodo-benzene (10 g.).	
15	Nitrobenzene (10 c.c.)	2.5	"	"	4†	No change.	
16	Toluene (10 c.c.)	2.5	"	"	4*	<i>o</i> - and <i>p</i> -Bromo- toluene (5.5 g.).	1.8 g. of penta- bromobenzoic acid.
17	<i>p</i> -Xylene	2.2	"	"	4*	5-Bromo-xylene (3.2 g.).	4-Bromo-xylene; ω -bromo- xylene (1.5 g.). Tetrabromo- xylene (1.9 g.).
18	<i>o</i> -Chloroto- luene (5 c.c.)	1.1	"	5	4*	No bromo derivative.	Chlorobenzoic acid (3.6 g.).
19	<i>p</i> -Iodo-tolu- ene (10 c.c.)	2.0	"	10	4*	No bromo derivative.	Iodo-benzoic acid (4.4 g.).

* Allowed to stand for two hours more.

† Allowed to stand overnight.

TABLE II.

Expt.	Benzene (in c. c.)	Bromine (in c. c.)	Acetic acid.	Conc. H ₂ SO ₄ .	Fuming H ₂ SO ₄ .	Time allowed for re- action (in hrs.)	Monobromo- derivative (in gm.)	Poly-bromo- derivative.
1	10	3	...	10 c.c.	...	4	3.2	...
2	"	6	...	10 c.c.	...	4	3.8	3.2 g. of <i>p</i> -di- bromoben- zene.
3	"	3	...	...	20 c.c.	4	4.3	0.9 g. of <i>p</i> -di- bromoben- zene.
4	"	4	...	...	10 "	2	6.1	...
5	"	4	...	...	15 "	2	7.0	...
6	"	5	...	...	10 "	2	7.4	A little of di- bromoben- zene.
7	"	6	...	...	10 "	2	8.3	0.8 g. of dibro- mobenzene.
8	"	6	3 c.c.	...	10 "	2	7.2	0.6 g. of dibro- mobenzene.
9	"	6	...	...	15 "	2	8.5	0.6 g. of dibro- mobenzene.
10	"	6	3 c.c.	...	15 "	2	7.9	0.8 g. of dibro- mobenzene.
11	"	6	...	...	20 "	4	little	5.5 g. of dibro- mobenzene.
12	Benzene sulphonic acid 5 g.	3	...	...	...	4	no bromina- tion.	...
13	Toluene 10 c. c.	2.5	...	...	10 "	2	5.0	...
14	Toluene 10 c. c.	3.5	...	...	10 "	2	6.8	...
15	Xylene 10 c. c.	2.5	...	...	7 "	2	bromo-deri- vative mainly 5- bromo-xy- lene (5.8).	...

Bromination in presence of concentrated or fuming nitric acid or a mixture of nitric and sulphuric acid.

The procedure adopted in this case is the same as that described in the preceding ones. The results obtained are summarised below. Concentrated nitric acid used in these experiments has the sp. gr. 1.44 while fuming nitric acid has the sp. gr. 1.52. Fuming sulphuric acid contains about 10 per cent. of sulphur trioxide.

TABLE III.

Expt.	Benzene (in c.c.)	Bromine (in c.c.)	Conc. HNO ₃ (in c.c.)	Fuming HNO ₃ (in c.c.)	Conc. H ₂ SO ₄	Fuming H ₂ SO ₄	Time allowed for re- action (in hrs.)	Mono- bromo- deriva- tive (in gms.)
1	10	3	10	...	...	...	4	1.9
2	"	"	...	10	...	...	"	8.6
3	"	"	...	5	...	5 c.c.	"	8.8
4	"	"	...	8	...	2 c.c.	"	7.2
5	"	"	...	5	5 c.c.	...	"	6.2

4. Bromination in presence of sodium nitrite and concentrated or fuming sulphuric acid.

The experiments have been carried out in this case by taking benzene, bromine and sodium nitrite in a round-bottomed flask which is heated on a water-bath. When the benzene begins to boil, sulphuric acid is added from the upper end of the condenser one c.c. at a time at interval of ten minutes. The flask is vigorously shaken from time to time, when the whole of the acid is added, the reacting mixture is further allowed to be heated on the water-bath till 4 hours are completed. The resulting product is first washed with water, then with dilute caustic soda solution and finally again with water. It is dehydrated with fused calcium chloride and distilled as before. The results obtained are summarised below.

TABLE IV.

Expt.	Benzene (in c.c.)	Bromine (in c.c.)	Sodium nitrite (in gms.)	Conc. H ₂ SO ₄ (in c.c.)	Fuming H ₂ SO ₄	Time allowed for the reaction (in hrs.)	Mono- bromo- benzene (in gms.)
1	10	3	5	10	...	4	5
2	"	3	15	20	...	"	5.4
3	"	5	15	20	...	"	6.2
4	"	4	15	20	...	"	5.7
5	"	4	20	20	...	"	4.8
6	"	3	12	20	"	"	5.3
7	"	3	5	...	10 c.c.	"	5.8
8	"	3	15	...	15 c.c.	"	5.3
9	"	3	10	...	20 c.c.	"	6.2

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